

Beyond Traditional Dentistry: A Comprehensive Look at Digital Innovations

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Abstract

Digital dentistry has rapidly transformed the landscape of dental practice, ushering in a new era characterized by advanced technologies and innovative solutions. This article explores the evolution, applications, and clinical implications of digital dentistry. From digital imaging and diagnostic tools to computer-aided design and manufacturing (CAD/CAM) technologies, the integration of digital platforms has significantly enhanced precision, efficiency, and patient outcomes. This review discusses the key components of digital dentistry, including intraoral scanning, 3D printing, and computer-guided implantology, highlighting their impact on diagnostics, treatment planning, and the fabrication of dental prosthetics. Furthermore, the abstract addresses the challenges and opportunities posed by the digitalization of dentistry, emphasizing the need for ongoing education and adaptation within the dental profession. Ultimately, digital dentistry stands at the forefront of dental innovation, promising improved workflows, enhanced patient experiences, and a paradigm shift in oral healthcare delivery.

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Introduction

Digital dentistry is a set of dental technologies that employ computer-based techniques and instruments to deliver better dental services, using specific hardware and software. This technology includes a variety of computer-based treatments that can be applied to a broad range of medical conditions. It is a rapidly advancing field that utilizes inventive technologies to enhance various dental procedures. By incorporating tools such as 3D imaging, Computer-aided design and manufacturing (CAD/CAM), Virtual reality, 3D printing, digital smile design (DSD), and Teledentistry- Dentists can achieve higher levels of precision, better treatment outcomes, increase in productivity, efficiency, and patient satisfaction, while also being cost-effective. All these technologies are being used in various disciplines like orthodontics, periodontics, prosthodontics, implant dentistry as well as cosmetic dentistry, enhancing our

abilities to create personalized treatment plans for every patient and provide them with the best care.

Evolution of Digital Dentistry

A groundbreaking change in dental practices, digital dentistry seamlessly integrates technologies to improve patient care, efficiency, and precision. With the advent of cutting-edge tools and techniques, traditional methods have gradually given way to a digital era that is revolutionizing the imaging, diagnostics, treatment planning, and fabrication processes (Figure 1). This change represents a watershed in the history of dentistry since it not only optimizes dental work flows but also considerably raises the standard of dental care provided. We will examine the significant turning points and developments that have accelerated the development of digital dentistry and ushered in a new era of dental excellence in this succinct summary.

EVOLUTION OF DIGITAL DENTISTRY

A Brief History

Figure 1. Timeline for Evolution of Digital Dentistry.

Clinical Implications of Digital Dentistry

Digital dentistry's clinical implications have brought about a paradigm shift in oral healthcare that goes beyond conventional approaches. By utilizing modern technologies, digital dentistry has become a game-changing influence on all facets of clinical practice. The digital revolution in dentistry has raised the bar for everything from precision restorations and patient communication to diagnostic imaging and treatment planning (Figure 2). We examine the significant effects that these developments have on diagnosis, treatment outcomes, patient experiences, and the general direction of contemporary dentistry in this investigation of the clinical implications of digital dentistry.

Figure 2. Clinical applications of Digital Dentistry

1. Oral Surgery

Oral Surgery is a branch that deals with complex dental surgical procedures like tooth extractions, impaction surgery, reconstruction surgery, and many more. Traditional procedures were done with the help of radiographs, which gave a detailed view of the structures of the patient. In recent times, there has been a shift towards digital radiography, which involves using intraoral scanners Charge-Coupled Devices & Complementary metal oxide semiconductors (CCD, CMOS) to capture images in greater detail. One such advancement is the CBCT. It offers high-resolution cross-sectional views of the oral and maxillofacial structures. Surgeons use this information for precise preoperative planning, especially in complex procedures such as dental implant placement, orthognathic surgery, and jaw reconstructions.

Also, CBCT data can be used in TMJ Ankylosis surgery, where the surgeons can visualize the anatomy in 3 dimensions, classify the type of ankylosis, and plan the surgery accordingly. Post-surgery, CBCT can also be employed for post-operative monitoring of the surgery. This helps to assess the present condition, identify potential complications, and guide any necessary adjustments in the postoperative period.

Electronic Technologies in Local Anesthesia: The Wand (Henry Schein Dental) (also known as Computer-Assisted Anesthesia System or Single Tooth Anesthesia) was introduced to minimize pain during administration. Instead of a conventional syringe, it uses a foot pedal-operated pump delivery system to administer anesthesia at a steady, slow rate. The absence of a traditional syringe is said to lessen patient anxiety, especially in younger patients who may be alarmed by the sight of a dental syringe, and to lower pulse rate associated with certain injections like intraosseous or periodontal ligament injections. This alleviates pain especially in uncomfortable injections like palatal infiltration and incisive blocks. The Wand was comparable to a slow intraosseous injection in maintaining a normal patient's pulse, compared with a fast intraosseous injection that elevated the pulse. Another electronic gadget called DentalVibe is said to lessen the pain associated with anesthetic injections.

Another great advancement is the artificial Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR). They allow the surgeons to visualize and practice complex procedures in a virtual environment before performing them on the actual patients.

2. Orthodontics

Orthodontics is a specialized branch of dentistry that focuses on the diagnosis, prevention, and treatment of malocclusions, which are improper bites resulting from irregularities in the positioning of teeth or jaws. Orthodontists, dental professionals with specialized training in this field, employ various methods to correct misalignments, improve dental aesthetics, and enhance overall oral function. Common orthodontic treatments include the use of braces, aligners, and other devices designed to gradually reposition teeth and jaws, ultimately achieving a harmonious and functional bite. The goal of orthodontics is not only to enhance the appearance of the smile but also to contribute to long-term oral health and well-being.

Digital Photos: When it comes to orthodontic treatment, patients often have high-quality 2D photos taken from different angles, both inside and outside the mouth. These photos serve as a basic reference for the facial structure and soft tissues. While 2D photos are easy to understand, they may not provide enough diagnostic information about factors like distance and angle. However, there is good news. Facial scanners now offer a standardized 3D representation of a patient's facial surface. When combined with digital models and CBCT images, it creates a complete 3D virtual patient.

The way we analyze X-rays has undergone a significant transformation. In the digital era, there are four recognized methods for interpreting these X-rays: the traditional approach involved manually tracing the skeletal soft tissue and dental features on an acetate overlay placed on the cephalometric radiograph. Landmark identification and measurements between landmarks were then taken. The second method utilized a digitizer connected to a computer which converted the traced paper into a digital format. The third approach involved directly digitizing lateral cephalometric X-rays using a digitizer connected to a computer followed by manual landmark localization. Currently, there is a growing trend towards fully automatic landmark identification through the implementation of artificial intelligence.

Digital Models: Usually, plaster or stone has been used to create them. Digital models have been developed to address several issues with traditional models, including longevity, portability, storage, and retrieval. They also offer a number of benefits, such as the elimination of the need for

a laboratory procedure, the creation of multiple diagnostic setups, the need for physical storage space, quick and easy retrieval at any location, the absence of physical damage risk, the ability to create indirect bracket bonding setups, accuracy in measurements such as tooth size, arch length, and width, space analysis, etc. They can also be shared via email with other dental professionals to support interdisciplinary treatment planning.

Aligners: By the late 1990s, Align Technology had launched clear aligner therapy under the brand name Invisalign, setting the standard for virtual models, virtual treatment plans, virtual setups, and appliance manufacturing with the aid of software developers. The same service is currently provided by numerous businesses, including Clear Correct, 3MTM (3M ESPE), and ClarityTM (Straumann) Aligners, among many more. Clinicians are now able to design and build their in-house aligners thanks to the digital workflow.

3. Pediatrics

Pediatric dentistry is a specialized field of dentistry that focuses on the oral health and dental care of infants, children, and adolescents. Pediatric dentists, undergo additional training beyond general dentistry to address the unique needs and concerns of young patients. This branch of dentistry encompasses various aspects, including preventive care, diagnosis, and treatment of dental issues specific to children, as well as education and guidance for parents on maintaining optimal oral health in their children. Digitalization in this specialization has paved a pathway for various clinical applications (Table 1).

Intra-oral scanners have completely changed the way dental impressions are made by digitizing scanned images of the oral tissues and making the process more comfortable and acceptable for patients—especially younger ones. The digital workflow of the manufacturing process has also made it much faster and simpler.

Applications in Pediatric Dentistry

Type	Year
Orthodontic space maintainer using PEEK polymer	2017
Anxiety free and patient friendly dental impression techniques in orthodontics	2018
Fixed Space maintainer (Band and toop)	2019
Cleft tip Cleft Palate: Digital intraoral scanning techniques for fabrication of feeding appliance/ Obturator	2019
For dental educational Purpose in cariology/endodontics	2019
Rapid Maxillary Expansion made up of titanium grade 5(CAD/CAM) maxillary expander with two mini screws and a 3D printed surgical guide	2020
TMJ disorders parafunctional habits (CAD/CAM fabricated occlusal bites-splints)	2020
Fixed space maintainer (Lower lingual holding arch space maintainer)	2020
Removable space maintainer made of PEEK material	2020
Speech aid appliance/palatal obturator for oro-nasal fistula	2021
Restorative dentistry, Chair side Zirconia crown fabrication	2021
Orthodontic therapy: “Zero expander” for constricted maxillary arch of PEEK material	2021
Myofunctional appliance (Functional Regulator of Type 3)	2021

Figure 3. The applications of Digital CAD/CAM/3D Printing for Pediatric Dentistry in recently published literature.

When creating space maintainers: CAD-CAM or 3D-printing technologies have been utilized to create space maintainers with enhanced accuracy and convenience in digital workflow by capturing a replica of the hard and soft tissues of the oral cavity using digital 3D intraoral scanners. Cleft lip and Cleft palate (CCLP) patients receiving prosthetic dentistry treatments: Since impression material can dislodge or block airways, imprint-making is a laborious, dangerous, and technique-sensitive activity when creating feeding appliances or obturators for newborns or infants with CLCP. However, recent literature has revealed that the introduction of intraoral scanning techniques and digital dentistry technologies has made intraoral imprints safer, more accurate, and more effective for pediatric CLCP patients.

For the constrained maxillary arch's expansion: In the pediatric age group, the zero-expander was described as a preprogrammed device to expand the narrow dental arch in both the deciduous and mixed dentition stages. Zero-Expander made of PEEK (Polyether ether ketone) material was used to treat a patient in the deciduous dentition stage, whereas a Zero-Expander made of PA12 material was used to treat a patient in the mixed dentition stage.

Regarding parafunctional tendencies temporomandibular joint diseases and bruxism. Bite splints/occlusal splints are widely utilized for parafunctional behaviors (bruxism), temporomandibular joint-related diseases, and also for disharmonious-occlusion difficulties. Traditional techniques for preparing these appliances involve the use of vacuum thermoforming or acrylic resins. However, a new study found that the accuracy of bite splints utilizing CAD/CAM technology with two different manufacturing processes, namely milling and 3D printing, were equivalent and of the same quality in terms of precision.

4. Prosthodontics

It is a specialized field of dentistry that focuses on the restoration and replacement of missing or damaged teeth. Also known as dental prosthetics or prosthetic dentistry, this branch of dentistry involves the diagnosis, planning, and execution of various treatments to restore oral function, esthetics, and comfort. Prosthodontists, the dental specialists in this field, work with a wide range of dental prostheses, including crowns, bridges, dentures, dental implants, and other devices designed to replace or repair teeth (Figure 3).

Figure 4. Applications of Digital Dentistry in Prosthodontics

CAD/CAM

Inlays, onlays, veneers, fixed partial dentures, implant abutments, implant crowns, surgical guides, full dentures, and maxillofacial prostheses are all made using CAD/CAM technology. The use of CAD/CAM offers accuracy, precision, and preservation of acquired digital information while significantly reducing chair side time. The application of CAD/CAM technology was intensively pursued by three research systems: The French System, the Minnesota System, and the Swiss System

Dental material testing using digitalization:

Digitalized testing has improved the efficiency of testing dental materials' mechanical, biological, and physical characteristics. With the introduction of finite element analysis, the material or design's mechanical properties, stress imparted by different materials, and the impact of various designs on dentofacial structures, implant location, and loading are all analyzed using a computer model.

Digitalization in training and education of dental students: In the past, trainees were taught how to do surgery under the guidance of experts; however, this approach proved to be expensive, time-consuming, and inconsistently effective. Dental students can practice on a three-dimensional simulated oral cavity with virtual reality instruction.

Digital articulators: With a jaw movement analyzer, virtual condylar and incisive guidance can be quantified precisely. By mimicking mandibular movement, these virtual articulators allow prosthesis creation on a kinematic level.

The process of creating mechanical models automatically from graphical computer data is known as rapid prototyping or RP. RP uses a range of technologies to produce certain parts from CAD models in a matter of hours, all without the need for human intervention.

With an accuracy rate of 0.1 to 0.4 mm, it is utilized in the manufacture of obturators, surgical stents, burn stents, and nasal and auricular prostheses.

Digital shade matching: The most popular technique is visual shade matching; however, it differs based on the clinician's color vision and experience, the lighting, the dentist's background, and the kind of shade guide utilized. A digital camera can record digital data, which can then be analyzed by the right image software to provide an accurate shade selection. Selecting colors digitally is more practical and can offer the full range of colors available in real teeth.

Digital impressions. There are several digital impression systems on the market, including the Lava™ chairside oral scanner, the E4D dentist system, the Cerec system, and the iTero system. Key characteristics including operation mechanism, light source, need for powder coating spray, operational procedure, and output file format are where they differ from one another. The efficiency of digital impressions is noticeably higher than that of traditional impressions.

5. Periodontics

Periodontics is the branch of dentistry that focuses on the prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of diseases and conditions that affect the supporting structures of the teeth, including the gums and bone. Periodontal treatments may involve scaling and root planing (deep cleaning), gum surgeries, regenerative procedures, and dental implant placement. Periodontists also play a key role in educating patients about oral hygiene practices to prevent and manage periodontal issues.

The following are the clinical implications of digital dentistry in periodontics:

3D advancement in periodontal probing: Ultrasonography periodontal probing is a method for periodontal ultrasonic diagnostics, involving the projection of maximum frequency arrow ultrasonic beam to periodontal pockets. The periodontal ligament reflects the echoes of the ultrasound waves which are captured by the transducer positioned within the handpiece which is transferred to the system for evaluation. The ultrasonic image is built and the software converts data for estimating periodontal pocket depth. However, this approach is challenging, as the interpretation requires visualization and analysis of an echo wave. Endoscopic capillaroscopy is a versatile endoscope that utilizes fiber optics to visualize distant inaccessible internal structures. Optical fiber technology may obtain a higher-resolution picture of the periodontal pocket microcirculation.

Utilization of AI Technology in the detection of dental plaque: Dental plaque comprises bacterial masses on dental surfaces; this mass typically occurs on the gingival margins and interproximal areas. The AI model used to detect plaque was developed based on a conventional neural network (CNN) and trained using images to fine-tune the system based on the transfer

learning method. Photographs of primary teeth were taken using an intraoral camera after this disclosing agent was applied and photographs of the discolored teeth were taken. Areas with a plaque were marked on natural teeth and discolored teeth. The adopted plaque detection model then gathered the features of dental plaque from these images. The dental plaque observed by the AI model was compared to the actual dental plaque areas to enable the AI model to compare the results and learn from its errors. When observation was made in detecting the plaque by the clinician and AI model, better and more accurate results were obtained from the AI model. This would become more helpful in the prevention of the accumulation of plaque and the progression of periodontitis.

T Scan system in Periodontics: T scan has been commonly used as a reliable and easy-to-use diagnostic method for occlusal contact analysis using paper-thin disposable sensors. The T scan makes the quantity of measurable contact data by recording variables such as bite duration, time, and intensity of tooth contact and saves data on the hard disc that can be played over time-based video for data analysis. The difference in electrical resistance is transformed into photos on the screen. The program works in two ways: time analysis and force analysis. Time analysis mode includes details on the position and duration of contacts displayed on the previous screen with the first, second, and third or more contacts in various colors. The force analysis mode demonstrates the position of occlusion and their relative intensity in five separate colors.

Computerized Local anesthetic delivery: Periodontal procedures involve the injection of a local anesthetic solution to prevent pain during clinical situations like Scaling and Root Planing, flap surgery with localized defects, and the harvesting of the free mucosal grafts from the palate. The computer-controlled local anesthetic system was introduced in 1997. It consists of a base unit, handpiece, and foot pedal. The handpiece is an ultralightpen-like handle in which the traditional anesthetic cartridge is mounted. It has a base unit that contains a microprocessor that controls a piston that incorporates local anesthetics by pushing the local anesthetic plunger up into the cartridge. The solution is pushed through the micropore tube of a handpiece operated by a computer control device. It is non-threatening to the patient due to the reduced force required for needle insertion and this makes the patient more comfortable.

Digital smile designing: A software-based system enabling the clinician to see and gauge the discrepancy between orofacial and dentogingival tissues. It is an accurate & effective method for aesthetic rehabilitation. It uses digital editing software in addition to digital photography. DSD makes treatment planning easier to understand by breaking down the steps into simpler steps. It validates the expectations of the patient, which increases treatment acceptance. For patients seeking aesthetic correction, these simulations can offer a range of treatment options and anticipated results. The software uses the data gathered from the photos to create an aesthetically pleasing treatment plan. Provisional restorations or wax mock-ups will give the patient and the clinician a preview of the outcome after aesthetic evaluations are completed. Treatment is more predictable when patients can see the intended outcome. By providing patients with a digital presentation of the outcome and educating them about the advantages of the treatment, the physician could allay their fears. It improves clinician evaluation and treatment plans through cosmetic simulation of patients' issues by digital analysis of gingival, facial, and dental parameters.

3D Printing: The term "3D printing" refers to the process of adding substance through layer-by-layer construction. To fabricate the precise reproduction of each item, it makes use of data from CAD programming that estimates a large number of cross segments. Tissue scaffolding for bone grafting operations is provided by 3D printing. Bio-resorbable scaffolds are used in 3D printing for periodontal reconstruction, procedures involving sinus and bone augmentations, direct implant installation, and peri-implantitis maintenance. Facilitating the regeneration of bone, PDL, and cementum, and the establishment of linkage between them is the aim of 3D-printed scaffolds. It is now possible to preserve the extraction socket's dimensions and retain the socket by using 3D-printed scaffolding enhancing osteogenesis and lowering the risk of inflammation. The use of 3D printing techniques in the development of medications could aid in the production of particular medications. These drugs would be precise, dose-dependent, safe, and efficient.

3D-assisted Implant surgery: When a patient's teeth are replaced, they must meet the biomechanical, functional, and aesthetic requirements for a natural dentition—particularly for chewing. The clinical outcome is frequently unpredictable when conventional procedures are involved

because it primarily depends on the knowledge and experience of the practitioner. Advancements in computer-assisted surgery have contributed to the concept of successful procedures in Implantology. The guided techniques usually concentrate on the 3D reconstruction of the anatomy data obtained from CBCT or Computed Tomography (CT). Digital drill guide models, which are typically produced by stereolithography, are a part of digital planning processes. Several manufacturers have recently developed and received clinical approval for pertinent 3D image-based system programs for implant surgery planning

6. Public Health Dentistry

Public health dentistry is a specialized field within dentistry that focuses on promoting and improving oral health at the population level. It involves the application of principles and practices of public health to prevent and control dental diseases, promote dental health, and enhance the overall well-being of communities. Public health dentists work to address oral health disparities, reduce the prevalence of dental diseases, and improve access to dental care for diverse populations.

Digital imaging in oral epidemiology: Digital imaging has shown to be a useful technique in the field of oral epidemiology, helping to overcome the drawbacks of direct clinical assessment. According to recent studies, digital imaging can effectively ensure examiner blinding by enabling remote scoring of anonymized images, thereby reducing observer bias. Standardizing examination conditions and cutting down on training and calibration time are two more benefits of having multiple examiners evaluate the images concurrently from various locations.

Digital risk assessment models and screening tests: Images are used by the Electronic Oral Health Screening System (EOHSS) to identify and evaluate oral conditions. It is intended for use in the field by dental hygienists, dentists, and other qualified personnel. Digital caries risk prediction models such as CAMBRA, Cariogram, and CRAFT have demonstrated efficacy in estimating dental decay risk in various population subsets. There are risk assessment models for periodontal disease, including the Risk Assessment-Based Individualized Treatment (RABIT) and the Periodontal Risk Calculator (PRC). A new avenue for periodontal disease mapping and screening has been made possible by genetic testing. Additionally, fluorosis in communities is mapped and classified using dual-camera systems equipped with innovative software algorithms.

Digital health records: Comparing electronic health records to paper-based systems reveals numerous benefits. By requiring structured data entry, they promote adherence to documentation standards and help to ensure accuracy and consistency. They also make it possible to monitor and make information sharing easier for members of the healthcare team. It is imperative to acknowledge that the caliber of the data input into these systems is of utmost importance. Even the best data algorithms won't work if the initial input isn't reliable or valid.

7. Conservative Dentistry & Endodontics

Conservative dentistry focuses on preserving and restoring natural teeth, emphasizing minimal removal of tooth structure. Common procedures include fillings, inlays, onlays, and crowns. Endodontics specializes in treating the dental pulp and tissues around tooth roots. Root canal treatment is a common procedure to address infections or inflammation and save teeth from extraction.

Pulp Vitality Versus Sensibility Testing

Pulp testing which has been around for many years, enables the medical professional to assess whether the pulp is necrotic or vital and, on rare occasions, to replicate the patient's main complaint. It is assumed that thermal or electrical stimuli can readily activate the actively conducting neurons found in the vital pulp. But sometimes, as with traumatic injuries, this assumption is incorrect. Pulp vitality is often retained after trauma, even though sensitivity is lost. Furthermore, current pulp-testing technologies are unable to accurately distinguish between reversible and irreversible pulpitis. For instance, persistent pain after applying cold therapy is frequently diagnosed as irreversible pulpitis, even though it's unclear how long and how severe the pain must remain for this diagnosis to be valid. Clinicians often misdiagnose irreversible pulpitis from the brief hyperalgesia that is typical of reversible pulpitis. This is significant because it is crucial to distinguish between the need for root canal therapy and conservative surgical techniques or vital pulp therapy. This is accurate regardless of whether the patient exhibits pulpal symptoms since pulpal symptoms are well-known to be localized.

Allodynia measuring device

Allodynia is the term used to describe percussion sensitivity because, in most cases, percussion does not

cause tooth pain. It can be used to diagnose periodontal abscess, occlusal trauma, cracked teeth (bite test), and periapical inflammation. A device was proposed to objectively measure mechanical allodynia by comparing the patient's occlusal force on a tooth to that of a normal contralateral tooth. According to a follow-up study conducted with this device, 57% of cases of irreversible pulpitis are associated with mechanical allodynia. When allodynia is diagnosed along with symptomatic irreversible pulpitis, it is crucial for clinical reasons because, if allodynia is absent, complete pulpal debridement—rather than just a pulpotomy—must be performed during the emergency visit to relieve the symptoms.

Using optical coherence tomography (OCT), an imaging technique, the structure of a biological tissue can be ascertained by examining the dispersed reflections of light near the infrared region. OCT is non-invasive and poses no biological risk. OCT-based dental technologies, however, are still in their infancy. In endodontics, OCT has been used to detect cracks in enamel or dentin and fractures of the roots vertically. Additionally, it has been utilized to detect periapical lesions that do not pierce the cortical bone. All of these attempts, though, have only been made in *ex vivo* models; at this time, there are no clinical devices that can be used for this purpose. This is a crucial clinical area because, in many cases, these clinical conditions are difficult to diagnose without surgical exploration or restoration removal.

As an imaging technique that is non-invasive and does not involve ionizing radiation, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) poses no health risks. It works by applying a powerful magnetic field to tissues, which causes hydrogen atoms to become excited. As the atoms return to their equilibrium state, their resonant frequencies are detected. It was not until the advent of newer modifications of the technology, such as SWIFT- MRI, that image details potentially useful in endodontic applications could be shown. Cysts and periapical granulomas have been distinguished using dental or medical MRI systems, to find fractures in the roots and cracks, as well as to find dental pulp tissues that have grown back. Because of its safety, MRI is also being investigated as a guided endodontic treatment

Ultrasound Real-Time Imaging of Periapical Lesions: A further non-invasive imaging technique that doesn't use ionizing radiation is color-power Doppler

Ultrasound Imaging. When this technology was first introduced at the beginning of the twenty-first century, there was evidence that it could distinguish between periapical granulomas and cysts in addition to detecting the presence of periapical lesions confirmed by a more recent trial. Additionally, it helpstrace the course of sinus tracts with endodontic origins. Nonetheless, radiographic methods are still widely acknowledged to be more accurate than ultrasound, and at this point, treatment planning is not affected by the distinction between granuloma and cyst. Due to its anti-inflammatory and disease-suppressive properties, there has been some interest in using ultrasound to help dental lesions heal; however, not enough research has been done in this field of dentistry.

Magnification Technologies: Microscopes, video scopes, and Endoscopes

While many dentists now use magnifying loupes, particularly those with additional lighting sources, endodontic applications require a higher level of illumination and magnification that can only be achieved by surgical operating microscopes and endoscopes. According to one study, endodontists who used dental loupes or microscopes were equally likely to locate Mesio-Buccal2 (MB2) canals in maxillary molars. More recently, research has demonstrated that treating maxillary first molars without the use of microscopes is linked to a notable rise in the number of missed MB2 canals and the frequency of apical radiolucency of the MB root. The prognosis for endodontic surgery has dramatically improved recently, being linked to the use of the microsurgical technique. However, it should be highlighted that the microsurgical technique uses much more biocompatible materials for filling—mineral trioxide aggregate—and reduces the angle at which the root is resected. Additionally, ultrasonic root-end preparation minimizes the size of the osteotomy. Using microscopes in treatment enables the integration of several digital technologies for improved case documentation, patient communication, and referral dentistry. Videoscopy, also known as video microscopy, is another digital technology that is becoming somewhat more and more popular. With this technology, illumination magnification is possible at a power similar to that of microscopy. It permits complete recording of the procedure, which can then be viewed by the provider, assistants, and/or trainees on one or two high-definition monitors.

Sonic, Ultrasonic, and Multisonic Technologies

Active root canal instrumentation was traditionally performed using files that were activated by ultrasonic or analog sonic devices. These devices were demonstrated to be more aggressive than conventional hand instrumentation in certain situations and to be no more effective than standard instrumentation. Nowadays, pulp stones, tertiary dentin, posts, and root canal obstructions are removed, and root end cavities are prepared for endodontic surgery using ultrasonic devices, which are commonly used in endodontic access preparation. Passive sonic or ultrasonic irrigation and needle activation during sonic or ultrasonic irrigation have also been used in devices designed to enhance root canal debridement and cleaning. Ultrasonic tips have the advantage of being narrow, which allows for precise cutting and does not allow the handpiece head to interfere with visualization under a microscope.

Impacts of digital dentistry:

Digital dentistry has affected dentists and patients in a variety of ways, both positively and negatively (Figure 4). Positively, CAD/CAM technologies streamline treatment planning, improve procedural precision, and provide dentists with improved diagnostic capabilities through intraoral scanners and other tools. Because dentists can now visually explain treatment plans to patients, this improves patient communication while also increasing the efficiency of dental workflows. Furthermore, shorter treatment times, more precise treatments, and less invasive procedures all

contribute to patients' increased comfort and more predictable results. Better patient education and the personalization of dental treatments are two more benefits of digital dentistry. The adoption of digital dentistry is not without its difficulties, though, as there are upfront costs associated with the technology, ongoing professional development requirements, and possible privacy and data security risks. Finding the right balance between utilizing the advantages of digital innovations and resolving these issues is essential to guarantee the best possible results for patients and dentists.

IMPACTS OF DIGITAL DENTISTRY

Figure 5. Impacts of Digital Dentistry

Conclusion:

In conclusion, digital dentistry is a rapidly advancing field that incorporates various technologies to enhance dental procedures. These technologies such as 3D imaging, CAD/CAM, virtual reality, 3D printing, and Teledentistry, improve precision, treatment outcomes, productivity, efficiency, and patient satisfaction while also reducing costs. The use of digital technologies in dentistry is increasing, leading to better treatment outcomes, reduced need for retreatment, and increased job opportunities in the field. Additionally, the field of dentistry has evolved, adapting to new technologies and techniques, with a focus on preventive care and patient education.

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